

ENDOGLUCANASE PRODUCTION BY BACILLUS CIRCULANS STRAINS GU25 AND GU38

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Abstract:

Background: The aim of this study was to evaluate the ability of β -1, 3-endoglucanase production by *B. circulans*.

Methods: *Bacillus circulans* was cultivated in YMB media. In the next step, *B. circulans* was added to CMC (carboxy methyl cellulose) culture. The protein concentration and endoglu-canase activity were measured.

Results: The optimal pH and temperature for high endoglu-canase activity in the CMC culture were pH 5.5 and 40 C respectively. Under these conditions, isolate Gu38 with 3×10^{-13} $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{ml}$ showed the highest endoglucanase ac-tivity in this temperature.

Conclusion: This study led us to conclude that *Bacillus circu-lans* strain Gu38 may serve as good source of endoglucanase production.

Keywords: *Bacillus circulans*, Endoglucanase, strain Gu38,